

Monometallic and heterobimetallic complexes involving dioxouranium(VI) and dioxouranium(VI)-zinc(II) with disalicylaldehyde-acyloyl- and -phthaloyldihydrazones

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The complexes of the compositions $[\text{UO}_2(\text{H}_3\text{salligh})(\text{OAc})].3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $(\text{UO}_2\text{Zn}(\text{salligh})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2).2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, where $\text{H}_4\text{salligh}$ refers to disalicylaldehyde-oxaloyldihydrazone ($\text{H}_4\text{salo}\text{xlh}$), -malonoyldihydrazone ($\text{H}_4\text{salm}\text{lh}$), -succinoyldihydrazone ($\text{H}_4\text{sals}\text{uch}$), -glutaroyldihydrazone ($\text{H}_4\text{salg}\text{luth}$), and -phthaloyldihydrazone ($\text{H}_4\text{salph}\text{th}$) have been synthesized. The complexes have been characterized by molar conductance and spectral data.

The dioxouranium(VI) complexes have possible application in solar energy conversion systems^{1,2} due to spectral properties, excited state life-times and electron transfer properties. Consequently, considerable attention has been paid to the synthesis and characterization of uranyl complexes with a variety of ligands in the last few years^{2,3}. Recently, dioxouranium(VI) complexes of multidentate polynucleating ligands have been synthesized since such ligands may produce unusual binuclear complexes containing different metal ions⁴. The properties of a metal ion are markedly modified when the second metal centre is present in its vicinity in the same structural unit due to the heterometallic nature of the system¹. The UO_2^{2+} ion is an electron-deficient metal ion and Zn^{2+} is an electron-rich metal ion. As a result, the properties of UO_2^{2+} ion would be markedly altered if both of them are present in the same structural unit of the complexes. Moreover, interest has also been shown in the heterobimetallic complexes containing two different metal ions usually from the same or neighbouring group⁵ and widely divergent transition metals. The acyloyl- and aroyl- and pyridoyldihydrazones derived from condensation of *o*-hydroxyaromatic aldehydes and ketones with acyloyl-, aroyl- and pyridoyldihydrazines are a few examples of ligands which yield dinuclear and polynuclear complexes^{6,7}. A survey of literature reveals that although some work on monometallic and homobimetallic complexes of a very few dihydrazones has been done, the work on their heterobimetallic complexes is virtually absent⁷. In view of the above importance of uranium complexes and absence of work on heterobimetallic complexes of dihydrazones, it was of interest to synthesize a series of heterobimetallic complexes containing UO_2^{2+} and Zn^{2+} ions derived from the title ligands. Further, we have isolated monouranyl complexes of the title dihydrazones which have been used as precursors for the synthesis of heterobimetallic complexes.

Results and Discussion

The reaction of uranyl acetate dihydrate with salicylaldehyde and dihydrazides in 1 : 2 : 1 molar ratio results in the formation of solid monometallic compounds. The analytical data are in accord with the formulation $[\text{UO}_2(\text{H}_3\text{salligh})(\text{OAc})].3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (where, $\text{H}_4\text{salligh} = \text{H}_4\text{salo}\text{xlh}-\text{H}_4\text{salph}\text{th}$). The reaction of these complexes with zinc acetate dihydrate in aqueous ethanolic medium with its slightly more quantity than required by 1 : 1 molar ratio, led to the precipitation of heterobimetallic complexes of the composition $[\text{UO}_2\text{Zn}(\text{salligh})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2].2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in which all the labile protons are removed, suggesting the tetrabasic nature of the ligands.

In order to offer confirmation of the core bridged bimetallic structures for the heterobimetallic complexes, an attempt was made to isolate heterobimetallic complex of UO_2^{2+} and Zn^{2+} from salicylaldehyde benzoylhydrazone under variety of conditions. The IR spectra of the products did not show band characteristic of uranyl ion, ruling out the possibility of the formation of heterobimetallic complex. Such a behaviour of salicylaldehyde benzoylhydrazone towards the formation of heterobimetallic complex suggests that the monoacyloyl-, monoaroyl- and monopyridoyldihydrazones behave differently as compared to those of the acyloyl-, aroyl- and pyridoyldihydrazones, and do not form heterobimetallic complexes whereas the dihydrazones do so readily.

The complexes isolated in the present study together with their colour, analyses, decomposition temperature and molar conductivity data are summarised in Table I. All the compounds decompose above 300°. The compounds could not be crystallized since they are mostly insoluble in water and common organic solvents. The monometallic complexes dissolve in coordinating solvents like DMF and DMSO while all the heterobimetallic complexes are insoluble in DMF but dissolve with difficulty in DMSO except complex 10 which is insoluble in both DMF and

DMSO. Complexes **1-5** showed weight-loss corresponding to three water molecules at 110° while for complexes **6-10**, the weight-loss corresponded to two water molecules only. No weight-loss was observed at 180° in complexes **1-5**, while in **6-7** the weight-loss corresponded to two water molecules. Loss of water molecules at 180° suggests that they are part of the coordination sphere in the complexes⁸, while that at 110° is part of the lattice structure of the complexes. The molar conductance of complexes **1-9** in DMSO falls in the range 0.5–1.7 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ suggesting that they are non-electrolyte⁹.

The ir and ¹H nmr spectra of the complexes **1-5** are consistent with the involvement of one C=O, one phenolic and two C=N groups in coordination to the metal centre. This is evident from the fact that in their ir spectra one amide-I band undergoes red-shift by 13–53 cm^{-1} while the other amide-I band weakens in intensity and remains almost unaltered. Further, the bands at 1573–1552 cm^{-1} (amide-II + $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ phenolic) split into several bands and suffer positive as well as negative shifts and appear at 1590–1565 and 1550–1500 cm^{-1} respectively, while some bands appear almost at the same position as in the uncoordinated dihydrazones but in reduced intensity. The ¹H nmr spectra of the complexes show signals at δ 11.87–11.10 (NH) and 12.67–11.80 (OH) which appear downfield compared to that of the free ligands. The involvement of both the C=N groups in coordination to the uranyl ion is evident from the appearance of only one either strong or very strong ir band in the region 1618–1605 cm^{-1} at low frequency by about 6–18 cm^{-1} (C=N) and singlet at δ 9.13–9.00 (CH=N) at downfield position by 0.79–0.14 ppm as compared to the dihydrazones in which they appear as doublet. Only the phthaloyldihydrazonato complex (**5**) shows a shift in $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ band to higher frequency. This suggests that in this complex electron density from phenyl ring of salicylaldimine part flows to the uranyl ion through the azine nitrogen increasing carbon and nitrogen bond order as has been reported in thiosemicarbazonato complexes¹⁰. In the other complexes, the drainage of the π -electron density of the phenyl ring occurs towards the uranyl ion through oxygen. The flow of the electron density to the uranyl ion through the azine group can be attributed to the replacement of methylene groups by the central phenyl ring which exerts electron-withdrawing power over the salicylaldiminato phenyl ring in the phthaloyldihydrazone ligand. It is pertinent to mention that the ir spectrum of the phthaloyldihydrazonocopper(II) complex shows a negative shift in $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ frequency, an usual trend observed in general in acylhydrazone complexes^{11,12}. This may be due to smaller size and higher electronegativity of copper than uranium which puts a check on the electron-withdrawing power of the phenyl ring. The new ir bands at 1553–1545 and 1415–1390 cm^{-1} are assigned to $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{OCO})$ and $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{OCO})$ respectively, due to bridged bidentately coordinated acetato group¹³. The appearance of a new weak to medium intensity band at 860–850 cm^{-1} characteristic of tetraatomic

species $\text{M} \begin{matrix} \text{O} \\ \diagup \quad \diagdown \\ \text{O} \end{matrix} \text{M}$, indicates the presence of phenoxide bridging in the complexes¹⁴. The band characteristic of uranyl group appears in the region 914–908 cm^{-1} .

The products of $\text{Zn}(\text{OAc})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ with the monouranyl complexes (**1-5**) show absence of amide-I band in ir spectra, and OH and NH signals in the ¹H nmr spectra, confirming the enolization of the dihydrazones and consequent coordination to the zinc metal centre through enolate and phenolate oxygen atoms and hence the formation of the heterobimetallic complexes. Like the monouranyl complexes, these complexes also contain phenoxide bridging as is evident from the presence of medium to weak band at 855–845 cm^{-1} . The band characteristic of uranyl ion at 925–900 cm^{-1} confirms that it is retained in the complexes unlike that in the salicylaldehyde benzoylhydrazone. The –CH=N– nmr signal is shifted further down-field in the heterobimetallic complexes indicating stronger coordination between azomethine nitrogen and metal centres. The $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ band in the ir spectrum of the heterobimetallic complex (**10**) splits up in two bands at 1630 and 1615 cm^{-1} respectively. This leads us to believe that in the hydrazone part bonded to the uranyl ion, the flow of the phenyl ring electron density of the salicylaldiminato part occurs through the azomethine nitrogen to the metal centre, while in the hydrazone part bonded to the zinc centre, the flow of the phenyl ring electron density of the salicylaldiminato part occurs through the phenolate oxygen to the metal centre. This confirms the bonding of the different hydrazone parts of the dihydrazone molecule to the different metal ions.

In an attempt to study the effect of complexation on the coupling of $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ vibrations, either as such or in an enolized form and ligand coordination to the metal centres as a function of the number of methylene group, we compared the asymmetric stretching vibration of the uranyl group in various complexes recorded under identical conditions. It is interesting to note that $\nu_3(\text{UO}_2^{II})$ vibration in the monouranyl complexes decreases in the order : $\nu_3(\text{oxalh}) > \nu_3(\text{malh}) > \nu_3(\text{phth}) > \nu_3(\text{such}) \approx \nu_3(\text{gluth})$, whereas in the heterobimetallic complexes, it decreases in the order : $\nu_3(\text{oxalh}) > \nu_3(\text{malh}) \approx \nu_3(\text{phth}) > \nu_3(\text{such}) > \nu_3(\text{gluth})$. The successive decrease of $\nu_3(\text{UO}_2^{II})$ value must be attributed to the decrease of O=U=O bond order due to the coordination of carbonyl oxygen to the metal centres in monometallic complexes and enolate oxygen to the metal centres in the heterobimetallic complexes. In other words, the lowering of ν_3 appears to have taken place by the increasing drainage of π_{2p} -electron density from the oxygen of the C=O group to the metal centre, which has been facilitated by decreasing coupling between them. This observation enables us to infer that the coupling between two C=O groups of the coordinated ligands decreases with the increase in the number of methylene groups and lends support to the proposition made by Jain and Rivest from their studies on the oxamido and malonamido complexes¹⁵. It is

also evident that coupling between two C=O groups in keto form vanishes after succinoyldihydrazone while it continues upto glutaroyldihydrazone in enol form.

In monouranyl complexes, the effect of phthaloyldihydrazone in causing decrease in ν_3 value is greater than that of malonoyldihydrazone while in heterobimetallic complexes, it is similar to that of malonoyldihydrazone, but in each case it is less than that of succinoyldihydrazone. In phthaloyldihydrazone, the two hydrazone groupings may be considered to be separated from each other either by two carbon atoms as in the case of succinoyldihydrazone or by six carbon atoms. Accordingly, the phthaloyldihydrazone should have had the same effect in causing decrease in the ν_3 value as the succinoyldihydrazone or even more than that produced by any of the dihydrazone employed in the present study. However, its effect is less than that of succinoyldihydrazone in each case. This means that C=O groups in phthaloyldihydrazone are more coupled to one another than those in succinoyldihydrazone. Such a feature associated with the phthaloyldihydrazone ligand in causing a decrease in ν_3 value must be attributed to the participation of the π -electron density of the central phenyl ring in it in coordination which exerts electron-withdrawing power over the two salicylaldimine phenyl ring.

A close examination of the asymmetric stretching frequency of the uranyl group shows that ν_3 in the heterobimetallic complex **6** occurs at higher frequency than that in the corresponding monometallic complex **1**, while in the other heterobimetallic complexes, the asymmetric stretching vibration of the uranyl group occurs at lower frequency than that in the corresponding monometallic complexes. Such opposite trend in heterobimetallic complexes may be due to the coordination number of the uranium atom and overlapping of $5f$ -orbital of uranium atom with $3d$ -orbital of zinc atom coupled with the coupling between two hydrazone grouping of the ligands. The decrease in coordination number of uranium atom (C.N. **6**) in the heterobimetallic complexes (**6-10**) as compared to those in the corresponding monometallic complexes (**1-5**) (C.N. **9**) must have raised the ν_3 values in all the heterobimetallic complexes compared to that in the corresponding monometallic complexes. The decrease in ν_3 values in the hetero-bimetallic complexes **7-9** is, most probably, due to overlapping of completely vacant $5f$ -orbital of uranium atom with completely filled $3d$ -orbital of zinc atom either directly or via super exchange mechanism involving oxo-bridged phenolic oxygen atom. The overlapping between vacant $5f$ -orbital of uranium atom and filled $3d$ -orbital of zinc atom is increasingly facilitated with decreasing coupling between the two hydrazone parts of the ligands selected in the present study which decreases with increasing methylene chain-length. The stronger coupling between two hydrazone parts in disalicylaldehyde oxaloyldihydrazone, most probably, prohibits the effective overlapping between completely vacant $5f$ -orbital of uranium and filled $3d$ -orbital of zinc leading to very small overlap-

ping, while successive decreasing coupling between hydrazone parts in remaining ligands with increasing methylene chain-length facilitates the increasingly greater expansion of $5f$ -orbitals of uranium atom and thus facilitating greater overlapping between vacant $5f$ -orbital of uranium and $3d$ -orbital of zinc¹⁶. The greater the overlapping between $5f$ -orbital of uranium and $3d$ -orbital of zinc, the greater will be the decrease in the extent of overlapping of $5f$ -orbital of uranium with the filled π_{2p} -orbital of apical oxygen atom resulting in the lowering of $\nu_3(\text{UO}_2^{\text{II}})$ as compared to those observed in the corresponding monometallic complexes.

Table 1. Analytical and molar conductance data of the complexes*

Compd./ (Colour, yield %)	Analysis % :		Mol. Cond. $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$
	Found/(Calcd.)		
	U	Zn	
[UO ₂ (H ₃ saloxlh)(OAc)].3H ₂ O (1) (Brown, 92)	33.1 (33.50)	-	0.5
[UO ₂ (H ₃ salmalh)(OAc)].3H ₂ O (2) (Brown, 85)	32.6 (33.0)	-	0.9
[UO ₂ (H ₃ salsuch)(OAc)].3H ₂ O (3) (Orange, 86)	32.0 (32.3)	-	1.3
[UO ₂ (H ₃ salgluth)(OAc)].3H ₂ O (4) (Brown, 84)	31.3 (31.7)	-	1.9
[UO ₂ (H ₃ salphoh)(OAc)].3H ₂ O (5) (Yellow, 75)	29.9 (30.4)	-	0.7
[UO ₂ Zn(saloxalh)(H ₂ O) ₂].2H ₂ O (6) (Brown, 95)	32.1 (32.6)	8.6 (9.0)	0.6
[UO ₂ Zn(salmalh)(H ₂ O) ₂].2H ₂ O (7) (Orange, 85)	31.8 (32.0)	8.8 (8.7)	0.8
[UO ₂ Zn(salsuch)(H ₂ O) ₂].2H ₂ O (8) (Yellow-orange, 87)	31.6 (31.4)	8.4 (8.6)	0.6
[UO ₂ Zn(salgluth)(H ₂ O) ₂].2H ₂ O (9) (Yellow-orange, 83)	30.9 (30.9)	8.5 (8.5)	0.5
[UO ₂ Zn(salphth)(H ₂ O) ₂].2H ₂ O (10) (Yellow, 40)	29.7 (29.6)	8.0 (8.1)	-

* All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses; decomp. temp. of all complexes = >300°.

In addition to the ligand bands (320–390 nm), which are red-shifted on complexation, the broad envelopes centered in the region 500–470 nm are observed in the electronic spectra of the monometallic complexes. These bands are assigned to electronic transitions from apical oxygen to f -orbitals of the uranyl moiety¹⁷. Further, this band may have contribution from charge transfer band arising from equatorial ligand atoms to the uranium atom. In the electronic spectra of the heterobimetallic complexes **6-9**, the band characteristic of uranyl moiety appears at 550–500 nm. These complexes show a new band in the region 475–410 nm which are different from the ligand bands. These bands arise from charge transfer from equatorial ligand atoms to the metal centre. The energy of this band increases in going from complex **6** to **9**, indicating increasing drainage of charge density from the π_{2p} -orbital of the carbonyl oxygen (enol) to the metal centres. However, in

complex **10**, the charge transfer band appears at 470 nm almost at the same position as in complex **6**. Although the electronic spectra of these complexes do not exhibit any additional non-ligand new band in this region, which can be assigned to the transfer of charge from the completely filled *3d*-orbital of zinc to the completely vacant *5f*-orbital of uranium atom resulted from their overlapping as deduced from infrared spectroscopy, the regular trend observed in an increase in the energy of the band in the region 475–410 nm in going from complex **6** to **9** suggests the strong possibility that this band may have contribution from electronic transition from zinc atom to uranium atom indicating the possibility of existence of $3d^{10} \rightarrow 5f^0$ transition¹⁶. Moreover, this band might be merged with the band in the region 550–500 nm due to UO_2^{II} moiety.

Based on the physicochemical evidences and considering the polymeric nature of the complexes, the bridging nature of the dihydrazones and the presence of oxo-bridged grouping involving phenoxide group, complexes **1-5** may be suggested to have the structure involving nine-coordinated uranium atom¹⁸. The fact that the $\nu_3(UO_2^{II})$ in complex **6** is higher than that in the corresponding monometallic complex and the interpretation of the observed lowering of the ν_3 vibration in the remaining heterobimetallic complexes as compared to those in their corresponding monometallic precursors in terms of overlapping of vacant *5f*-orbital of uranium and filled *3d*-orbital of zinc, rules out the possibility of coordination of water molecules to the uranium centre in the heterobimetallic complexes. Instead, it is suggested that both the water molecules present in the first coordination sphere are bonded to zinc centre only, although the problem can be solved unambiguously by X-ray crystallographic studies only.

Considering the presence of water molecules in the first coordination sphere around zinc centre in the heterobimetallic complexes, the presence of ligand bridging and $M \begin{array}{c} \diagup \\ \diagdown \end{array} M$ grouping and the incapability of salicylaldehyde benzoylhydrazone to form heterobimetallic complex, complexes **6-10** may be suggested to have the polymeric structure involving six-coordinated uranium and zinc atoms with octahedral stereochemistry. The linear uranyl group is surrounded by three oxygen atoms (one phenolate and one enolate oxygen atoms from half part of one ligand molecule, and one phenoxide bridged oxygen atom from half part of the second dihydrazone molecule) and one azomethine nitrogen atom from half part of the first dihydrazone molecule in the equatorial plane. The phenolate oxygen atom, enolate oxygen atom and azomethine nitrogen atom of the first half part of the second dihydrazone molecule and oxo-bridged phenoxide oxygen atom of the first half part of the first dihydrazone molecule occupy the equatorial positions around the zinc atom. In the structural unit, the uranium and the zinc atoms are bonded to one another through phenoxide bridges. The axial positions around uranium atom are occupied by oxo-oxygen atoms while around zinc atom by two water

molecules. The problem can be solved unambiguously only by X-ray crystallographic study.

Experimental

Uranyl acetate dihydrate, zinc acetate dihydrate, diethyl esters of oxalic, malonic, succinic, glutaric, and phthalic acids, ethyl benzoate, hydrazine hydrate, salicylaldehyde were of AnalaR grade. Acid dihydrazides, viz. oxaloyl-, malonoyl-, succinoyl-, glutaroyl-, and phthaloyldihydrazines were prepared by reacting the corresponding diethyl esters (1 mol) with hydrazine hydrate (2 mol). The dihydrazones¹⁹ were prepared by reacting aqueous or refluxing dilute ethanol solutions of the acid dihydrazides (1 mol) with salicylaldehyde (2 mol) and dried at 70°. Benzoylhydrazine¹¹ and salicylaldehyde benzoylhydrazone¹² were prepared by known procedures.

$[UO_2(H_3salligh)(OAc)].3H_2O$ (where $H_4salligh = H_4saloxlh-H_4salphth$) : To uranyl acetate dihydrate (1.8 g) dissolved in warm ethanol (100 ml) containing a drop of acetic acid was added salicylaldehyde (42.5 ml, 0.1 mol) in ethanol with stirring and the mixture was refluxed for 15 min. Acyldihydrazine (42.5 ml, 0.1 mol) in hot ethanol was added to it with stirring and the solution was refluxed for 2 h. The complexes obtained were filtered hot and again refluxed for 0.5 h in benzene, filtered hot, washed with hot C_6H_6 , C_2H_5OH , aqueous C_2H_5OH and Et_2O and dried over anhydrous $CaCl_2$.

$[UO_2Zn(salligh)(H_2O)_2].2H_2O$ (where $H_4salligh = H_4saloxlh-H_4salphth$) : To $[UO_2(H_3salligh)(OAc)].3H_2O$ (1.0 g) suspended in water (50 ml) was added $Zn(OAc)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ (0.05 ml, 35 ml) and the mixture was refluxed for 3 h. The resulting solid was washed with ethanol, benzene and Et_2O and collected in the usual manner.

Uranium and zinc were determined by standard methods²⁰. The dihydrazones were determined in 5 M H_2SO_4 . C, H and N were determined microanalytically. Molar conductance of the complexes (10^{-3} M in DMSO) was measured on an Elico CT-82T conductivity bridge. IR spectra (KBr/nujol) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 983 spectrophotometer, electronic spectra on a Carl-Zeiss VSU-2P spectrophotometer and 1H nmr spectra (DMSO) on a EM-3 (90 MHz) spectrometer using tetramethylsilane as internal standard.

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